

Cross-Layer Effect of Transmit Power in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

Bindeshwar S. Kushwaha
bindeshwar.kush@gmail.com
ORCID: 0000-0002-7335-9722

¹ and

Pramod K. Mishra
pkmisra@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0005-0667-1563²

^{1,2}Department of Computer Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India

Abstract

Level of transmit power in wireless ad hoc networks is critical, it decides the transmission range of a node and, thus, the connectivity of the network, the number of nodes within transmission range depends on the power level and, hence, the number of collisions, it affects hop count at the network layer and the throughput of the network, battery power also relies on transmit power level. However, very few papers quantitatively assessed the effect of transmits power on different performance parameters of different layers to optimize protocol performance and associated algorithms. In this paper, we evaluate and analyze cross layer effect of transmit power on the MAC, the network and the transport layers and analyse energy consumption, hop count, collisions, end to end delay, throughput, congestion window, and packet loss in ad hoc network.

Keywords- MANET, Transmit Power Control, Ad Hoc Networks

1 Introduction

Ad hoc network consists of mobile nodes and a node communicates without a base station or an access point with nodes, which are within its transmission range, and it uses multi-hop routing algorithms to communicate those nodes which are not within its coverage range, nodes in an ad hoc network are equipped power constraints, limited bandwidth and fully decentralized and communication among nodes depends upon co-operation of nodes transmit power play an important role in the optimal function of ad hoc network. Furthermore, value of transmitting power affects the function the physical layer, the MAC layer, the network layer and transport layer [1, 2], at the physical layer if transmit power is high signal quality at the receiver will be good and transmission range will belong but the high transmit power creates interference for other nodes. At the MAC layer high transmit power causes collisions, and at the network layer it reduces the number of hop counts, at the transport layer it causes congestion.

If the value of transmitting power is low, the receiver may not decode the signal and transmission range will be small but the magnitude of interference will be low for other nodes, at the MAC layer number of collisions will be low, and at the network layer low power can create a network partition [Figure 1]. Moreover, the transmit power also affects the energy consumed by a mode, high transmit power result in high energy consumption. Moreover, fixed transmit power approach consumes energy and sometimes does not allow concurrent transmission and causes degradation of network performance, however, variable transmit power can introduce asymmetric links [3] in the network and can pose specific challenges on the routing algorithms. In addition, the above problems must be quantized and evaluated using a simulator or real tested to see the experimental effect of transmit power on different parameter that can help understanding of protocols which are affected by transmit power, further, the tradeoffs among several parameters can be formulated as optimization problems and solved by optimization algorithms, in addition, where should power control be resided is a typical question when power control algorithms to be designed [4], however, from the simulation we will show that problems associated with transmit power is

(a) High Transmit Power Ad Hoc Network

(b) Low Transmit Power Ad Hoc Network

not concern of a single layer, but, it is a cross-layer problem and cross-layer algorithms should be designed to address transmit power related problems. Additionally, connectivity and capacity of mobile ad hoc networks depend upon the transmission power of nodes, very pioneer papers [5, 6] Addressed in this issue and derived the expression for the minimum transmission range for connectivity in multihop wireless networks i.e. $r(n) = \sqrt{\frac{\log n + k_n}{\pi n}}$ where k_n is connected components, n is number of nodes, $r(n)$ is transmission range of n nodes and $k \rightarrow \infty$, transmission range depends upon to transmit power, so, with the help of the relation between transmission range and k -connected components the minimum transmit power required for nodes in the network to be connected can be derived, connectivity is also a minimum requirement for a network to function. Furthermore, in section 2 we describe related work, in 3 we discuss about propagation models, in section 4 we explain about simulation environment, and from section 5 to 8 simulated results are discussed, and finally section 9 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

Extensive research has been done and still going on to evaluate the effect of transmit power on, energy consumption, MAC layer, mobility, network layer parameters, i.e. throughput, hop count, end to end delay, and routing load, and to adjust power dynamically algorithms are designed, [Pierre Chevillat et al.] proposed link adaptation algorithm to adjust power and data rate dynamically [7]. In [8], The authors analysed the effect of transmitting power in sensor network. In [9], authors proposed COMPOW protocol to minimize energy and maintain connectivity of the network. [Doggy et al.] analysed interference and transmit power control in 802.11 a/h wireless LANs. In [10], authors proposed power adjusting algorithm using the cross layer optimization technique to minimize the consumption of energy for wireless mobile ad hoc network, further, [11] discussed and analysed impact of transmission range on mobility and routing protocols in ad hoc network. In [12], NS-3 is used to analyse impact of node speed and transmission range on the hello interval of the MANET routing protocols, [13] analysed several power control approaches such as, node-degree constrained, location information based, graph theory, game theory, multi-parameter optimization approach, [14] evaluated effect of transmit power and antenna diversity on spectrum efficiency in cellular systems, and got the important result that there are trade off between spectral efficiency and reducing transmit power. Further, in [15] authors performed experiments and observed impact of transmit power in wireless sensor networks for low power transmission links using real testbed, in [16] impact of interference and transmit power control is analysed in 802.11 a/h network and proposed a method in which transmit power control resided at physical layer for rate adaptation and energy efficient network, further, [17] carried out work to observe effects of transmitting power and carrier sense on network capacity in multihop 802.11 network and derived expression for the throughput of each sender in the network, [18] proposed transmitted power control

algorithm called slow start power controlled for 802.11 MAC and improved energy consumption, throughput, and mitigate collisions, [19] The evaluated effect of transmit power on, packet delivery ratio, hop count, energy consumption, and normalized routing load in a mobile ad hoc network, transmit power also affect the capacity of the network, [20] quantitatively evaluated the effects of transmitting protocol on the capacity of the ad hoc network from the perspective of information theory. In [21] impact of variable transmit power on the network connectivity, network capacity, and on the physical layer is studied, authors in [22] argued that high transmit power increases throughput capacity of the network, and explained that in a wireless ad hoc network if all nodes are directly connected to each other with maximum transmit power this will be optimum topology, on the other hand, [23] proved that minimum transmit power and there is no any partition of the network can result in high throughput and minimum delay. Further, the emergence of low-power ad hoc sensor networks attracted the research on transmit power to minimize the energy consumption in the network, [24] conducted experimentally on 150 sensor nodes with different transmit powers and analyzed packet reception, asymmetry of the links, transmission range, collisions and latency. .

3 Radio Propagation Models

Radio propagation models are empirical formula which comes from observation and experiment which can be used to predict signal strength at the receiver, transmission range of the node, path loss, and propagation delay of the signals. Further, in wireless network each link has different characteristics and properties, such as, The frequency band of the channel, transmitted power, width of objects between sender and receiver, and these characteristics cannot be incorporated in a single propagation model, due to this, many propagation models are proposed. Some of them we describe.

3.1 Free Space Model

The free space model [25, 26] assumes perfect condition of propagation, and there is one line-of-sight path between transmit mode and receiving node and there is not any obstacles or source of impairment. Moreover, this model is suitable for satellite link modelling in which there is not an obstacle between sender and receiver.

$$P_r = \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^2 d^2 L} \quad (1)$$

and Path loss is

$$10 \log \frac{P_r}{P_t} = 10 \log(G_t G_r) + 20 \log(\lambda) - 20 \log(4\pi) db \quad (2)$$

Where

P_r	Received Power
P_t	Transmitted Power
G_t	Transmission Antenna Gain
G_r	Received Antenna Gain
λ	Wavelength
L	System Loss
d	Distance between sender and receiver

Moreover, the loss in received signal power is square inverse proportional to the distance from sender to receiver, this model shows ideal transmission range in the form of circle around node.

Signal path loss in free space model is

3.2 Two Ray Ground Reflection Model

In ray ground reflection model [26, 27] propagation path between sender and receiver, one is directing and another is reflected path from the ground. Further, the loss in receiving the power is inverse proportional to the fourth power of the distance from sender to receiver.

$$P_r = \frac{P_t G_t G_r h_t^2 h_r^2}{d^4 L} \quad (3)$$

and the Path Loss equation

$$10\log\frac{P_r}{P_t} = 10\log(G_t G_r) + 10\log(h_t h_r) - 40\log(d)db \quad (4)$$

Where

P_r	Received Power
P_t	Transmitted Power
G_t	Transmission Antenna Gain
G_r	Received Antenna Gain
h_t	Transmit Antenna Height
h_r	Receive Antenna Height
L	System Loss
d	Distance between sender and receiver

Typically the value of L is 1 [27].

In addition, the model also represents the circle of transmission range around the node, moreover, this model is very popular among researchers and we will also use this model in simulation.

4 Simulation Environment

The simulation is conducted using NS-2 [28] and area of simulation is 800 square meters, AODV [29] as routing protocol, TCP at the transport layer and at the application layer FTP is deployed. Further, 2.4 GHz band is considered as frequency band, and for MAC and physical layer IEEE 802.11 model is used in simulation. Moreover, other parameters can be seen in the table.

Table 1: Simulation Environment

Simulation Parameter(s)	Value(s)
Number of Nodes	10, 20, 30, 40, 50
Routing Protocol	AODV
Propagation Model	Two Ray Ground Reflection
Transport Layer	Transmission Control Protocol
No. of TCP Connections	4
Area	800 Square Meter
Network Simulator	NS-2
Application Layer	File Transfer Protocol
Transport Layer Protocol	TCP New Reno
MAC Layer	802.11
Frequency Band	2.40 GHz

Further, for TCP congestion window and throughput analysis we have taken six transmit power levels because four parameters are not sufficient to analyse the two parameters.

Additionally, table 2 shows the relation between transmit power and transmission range in two-ray ground reflection model, which we got in simulation environment which is given in table 2.

Table 2: Transmit Power and Corresponding Range

Transmit Power	Transmission Range
0.50	288.50
1.00	343.10
1.50	379.90
2.00	408.00
2.50	431.00
3.00	451.00

5 Effect on the Energy Consumption

Sending a single bit of information from the network interface consumes some amount of energy, since layered architecture of the protocol stack, it is necessary to capture effect of all the layers on the consumption of energy, the basic linear model [30], in terms of packet size and bandwidth acquisition, i.e. $energy - consumption = m * size + b$. This equation can be extended for more specific types of traffic such as, broadcast traffic, and peer-to-peer traffic. In terms of transmitting power energy consumption can be expressed as, i.e. $Transmitted_{energy} = transmittedpower * packetsize / 2 * 10^6$. From the latter models of energy consumption one thing can be noticed that transmitted energy is proportional to transmit power, which our simulation result shows. In addition, from the graph it can be observed that when the number of nodes increases, there is also an increase in energy consumption.

Figure 1: Energy Consumption

Further, when transmit power is increased then energy consumption i.e. both numbers of nodes and transmit power to affect battery power of a node, energy consumption by a node is directly proportional to the transmit power of a node. Moreover, when transmit power is 0.5 Watt for 10 nodes the lowest amount of energy is consumed, when it increased to 1.0 W then again energy consumption by nodes are increased and till transmit power 2.0 energy consumption is increased. Finally, it can be noticed that there is a directly proportional relationship between transmit power and energy consumption.

6 Effect on the MAC Layer

Unlike a wired network, a packet transmitted by a node is received by all nodes within its transmission range, i.e. wireless medium is inherently broadcast in nature. Furthermore, IEEE 802.11 ad hoc mode is the standard MAC layer which uses CSMA/CA (Carrier Sense Multiple Access / Collision Avoidance) to avoid collisions and RTS-CTS mechanisms [31] to avoid collisions due to a hidden node problem. However, RTS-CTS mechanism works well in certain conditions and it has still the possibility of collisions [32].

RTS-CTS Based Medium Access Procedure

- 1- Sender Sends RTS and Waits SIFS Time Interval*
- 2- Receiver Sends CTS to Sender and Waits SIFS Time Interval*
- 3- Sender Sends DATA to Receiver And Waits SIFS Time Interval*
- 4-Receiver Sends ACK to Sender*
- 5- Other Nodes Defer Transmission During this Interval*

The above mechanism avoids collisions at the MAC layer, but the interference causes by the hidden node (Node C) (A node that can be heard by the receiver (Node B) but not sender (Node A) Figure-3) can not be avoided.

Figure 3: Hidden Node Problem

As a result, in frame collision at the MAC layer, equation can be derived that how far should hide node be away from receiver, so that, interference from hidden node to receive can be prevented.

From equation 2

Received transmit power from sender node is

$$P_r = \frac{P_t G_t G_r h_t^2 h_r^2}{d^4 L} \quad (5)$$

Received interference power from hidden node is

$$P_r = \frac{P_t G_t G_r h_t^2 h_r^2}{d^4 L} \quad (6)$$

Received interference power from hidden node is

$$P_i = \frac{P_t G_t G_r h_t^2 h_r^2}{x^4 L} \quad (7)$$

Where x is distance between receiver and hidden node. Then

$$SNR = \frac{P_r}{P_i} = \left(\frac{x}{d}\right)^4 > SNR_{Threshold} \Rightarrow x > \sqrt[4]{SNR_{(Threshold)}} * d$$

Receiver should be $\sqrt[4]{SNR_{(Threshold)}} * d$ distance apart from hidden node to receive signal correctly.

From the simulation result, it can be stated that when the transmit power level is low number of collisions are lower, but when transmit power is increased number of collisions are also increased, but to transmit power 1.50 W collisions are always larger, the reason may be for transmit power level 1.50 W RTS-CTS mechanism is not effective.

Figure 2: Frames Collisions at the MAC Layer

7 Effect on the Network Layer

At the network layer transmit power level effects of several parameters and it is important to evaluate and see the impact of transmitting powerful effect on the interest of parameters like hop count, end to end delay, normalized routing load, throughput, and packet loss which is analysed and described below.

7.1 Hop Count Analysis

Transmit power of a node decides a number of hops between sources and destination pairs in the network, i.e. hop count at the network layer. Moreover, if transmission power is increased number of hop counts from source to destination are decreased

. From the figure, it can be seen that when transmission power is 0.50 Watt for 10 nodes, average hop count is 3, but when transmit power is increased average hop count is decreased i.e. transmission range is increased.

7.2 Normalized Routing Load (NRL) Analysis

The hop counts directly affects the normalise routing load (NRL), when the average hop counts value is larger than NRL value is also larger, but when transmit power is increased average hop count value is decreased and also the value of NRL is decreased, the reason behind result that, when transmit power is low and number nodes from source to is large each node has to process large number of control packets to route and forward data packets.

This can be understood by the following normalized routing load (NRL) equation [33].

$$NRL = \frac{P_c}{P_d} \quad (8)$$

Where

P_c **Number of Control Packets**

P_r **Number of Data Packets**

From the above equation, it can be understood that for a constant number of data packets control packets are increased if transmit power is low, since they're a larger number of hops, and when the power is increased average number of hops from source to destination are decreased and then NRL is decreased.

Figure 3: Hop Count Graph

Figure 4: NRL Graph

7.3 Delay Analysis

Again, the delay also transitively depends upon to transmit power to hop count and hop count to end to end delay. Further, when transmit power is increased number of hops are decreased. From the definition of end to end delay (EED)

$$EED = D_{trans} + D_{prop} + D_{proc} + D_{queueing} \quad (9)$$

Where

D_{trans}	Transmission Delay
D_{prop}	Propagation Delay
D_{proc}	Processing Delay
$D_{queueing}$	Queueing Delay

After analysing simulated results, it can be observed that when the value of transmit power is low end to end delay is high, because, when the power is low more number of hops will be from source to destination i.e. more number transmission links and that will contribute in transmission and propagation delay.

Figure 5: Delay Graph

Moreover, the number of hops contributes in queue and processing delay in the network, because if there are more nodes, then each node will have a queue then queuing delay and processing delay.

7.4 Throughput Analysis

Throughput is a very important parameter which measures overall performance of the network and transmit power also affects throughput, to see the effect we should observe the equation

$$Throughput = \frac{8 * TB}{TLBR - TFBS} \quad (10)$$

Where

- TB** Total Number of Bytes
- TFBS** Time at First Bit Sent
- TLBR** Time at Last Bit Received

Denominator of the equation TLBR-TFBS which is time taken by a single bit from source to destination, in addition, if transmit power is low the more number hops will be from source to destination, then there is more delay that implies lowering of throughput, however, very high transmit power also degraded throughput, because if transmit power value is high anode blocks communication between nodes those are within the node's range.

As a result, low throughput, further, there is no direct proportional relationship between transmit power and throughput, instead, there is an optimal value of transmit power for which throughput is optimal. Moreover, from the simulation result 1.50 W may be optimal value of transmit power for which the throughput is better than other transmit power levels.

7.5 Packet Loss Analysis

Furthermore, from the Figure-9 it can be noticed that the highest number packet losses transmit for the lowest power, power 0.50 Watt for any number of nodes, moreover, when transmit power is increased, i.e. 1.00 Watt packet losses are reduced, because transmission range is increased, the lowest number of packet losses is for transmitting power 2.50 Watt, however, when transmit power is increased to 3.00 Watt, again the number of

Figure 6: Throughput Graph

packet losses are increasing, this is because high transmit power causes interference for other node in the network and completion among nodes to acquire channel.

Figure 7: Packet Loss at the Network Layer

From the above discussion it can be concluded that, due to mobility, links may be broken, however, if nodes in the network transmit at the low power more number of link may be broken and it may create network partition, further, if source is in one network part and destination is in another then all the packets which are sent to destination will be lost. So, low transmit power saves energy but causes network partition and packet loss. However, high transmit power causes interference for other nodes in the network, and also competition among nodes to acquire channel, as a result in packet loss.

8 Effect on the Transport Layer

High transmit power causes congestion, which is a statement in [1], in figure 5 the plot between simulation time and dynamic congestion window size is plotted for different transmit power levels, further, when value of transmit power is 0.50 W the congestion window fluctuates from 1 to 10, the reason may be the transmit power level, which is small and mobility helps network to be partitioned, as a result, there is packet loss and if there packet loss TCP congestion control algorithm is executed and sender reduces its congestion window size i.e. reduction in data rate.

Figure 8: Congestion Window Size Graph

In addition, when transmit power is increased from 0.50 to 1.00 W then performance is better, and when transmit power is 1.50 W the best performance can be seen i.e it can be said that 1.50 W is optimal transmit power for TCP and configured network. Further, when transmit power is increased 2.00 W the performance is degraded, and when power is 3.00 W the worst performance can be noticed this is because, when the power is increased it creates high magnitude of interference and due to this receiver may not decode signal, as a result, packet loss and TCP interprets as congestion and reduces its congestion window size, as a result, reduction in throughput. its congestion window size, as a result, reduction in throughput.

9 Conclusion

To sum up, we can conclude that transmit power impacts on several performance parameters, such as, energy consumption is directly proportional to transmit power, collisions, hop counts are decreased when transmit power is increased, throughput, quality of signal, and magnitude of interference a node create for others, and there are also trade offs among performance parameters. Moreover, it is important to design power control algorithms while keeping tradeoffs among the parameters, further, connectivity and capacity, which also depend upon transmitting need to be addressed, the connectivity which is a minimal requirement for a network to be connected should be examined in mobile ad hoc networks. Furthermore, the cross layer optimization technique can help to solve these types of tradeoffs or optimization problems. In the future, we will focus to design cross layer algorithms and evaluate the performance of those algorithms on simulation tools or real testbeds.

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